

Rising Popularity of Wet Cupping (Hijama Therapy) in Karachi: Public Attitudes and Usage Trends

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Abstract

Introduction: Hijama therapy, or wet cupping, is a complementary alternative medical practice with deep historical and cultural roots. Its popularity has increased worldwide, including in Pakistan, due to its affordability, perceived health benefits, and religious significance. Despite its growing acceptance, limited research explores the reasons for its adoption, patient experiences, and global comparisons.

Objectives: This study aimed to examine the social, cultural, religious, and therapeutic factors driving the rising adoption of Hijama therapy in Karachi. It also explored patient experiences, including treatment outcomes, side effects, and sources of treatment.

Methodology: A prospective cross-sectional survey was conducted with 470 participants who went through Hijama therapy from various Hijama centers of Karachi. A structured questionnaire collected their demographic data, motivations, medical conditions treated, treatment outcomes, and side effects. Quantitative data like frequency and percentages were analyzed through its excel sheets, while qualitative responses underwent thematic analysis.

Results: Most participants were women (82.1%), aged 30–49 years. Religious significance (70.9%) and perceived health benefits (57.4%) were the primary motivators, followed by minimal side effects (26.7%) and dissatisfaction with conventional medicine (4.3%). Hijama was performed by trained practitioners (58.7%) and in professional clinics (68%). Musculoskeletal pain (47%), general body relaxation (33%), and genitourinary issues (29%) were common treatment reasons. Positive outcomes were reported by 95.5%, with minor side effects such as itching (38.8%) and pain (22.4%). Many combined Hijama with allopathy (34.9%), while 51.9% preferred it as a standalone treatment.

Conclusion: Hijama therapy is widely accepted in Karachi due to its cultural, religious, and therapeutic appeal. Increasing awareness of minor side effects and safety measures can further enhance patient satisfaction and treatment outcomes.

Keywords: *Hijama therapy, wet cupping, patient experiences.*

Suggested citation: Mushtaq, A., & Nini, D. (2025). Rising Popularity of Wet Cupping (Hijama Therapy) in Karachi: Public Attitudes and Usage Trends. *European Journal of Innovative Studies and Sustainability*, 1(3), 223-232. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejiss.2025.1\(3\).18](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejiss.2025.1(3).18)

Introduction

Hijama, or wet cupping therapy, is a traditional form of complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) that has been practiced for centuries across various cultures. While historically rooted in holistic healing traditions, it has gained renewed interest in recent years, particularly in the Middle East and South Asia, with increasing recognition in Europe and North America (Kouser, et al., 2021; Allafi, & Al-Haifi, 2020; Aboushanab, & AlSanad, 2021).

This therapy involves the application of suction cups to the skin, often following specific meridian points based on Chinese acupressure principles, which vary according to the underlying medical condition. The suction process is followed by superficial incisions to facilitate the removal of stagnant blood (Rahman, et al., 2017; Al-Rubaye, et al., 2021).

In recent years, Hijama has gained popularity due to its perceived therapeutic benefits in addressing chronic pain, migraines, and various other medical conditions. It has been incorporated into holistic healthcare frameworks, where it is believed to promote detoxification and enhance blood circulation (Mokhtar, Hassan, & Fahmy, 2018; Qureshi, Alkhamees, & Alsanad, 2018; Bhat, et al., 2024; Soliman, Hamed, & Khachemoune, 2018). Moreover, it is generally associated with minimal adverse effects, primarily limited to mild skin reactions (Zhou, Ruan, & Xing, 2014; Cao, et al., 2019).

Beyond its potential health benefits, Hijama holds religious significance in Islamic traditions, as it is considered a Sunnah practice attributed to Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him). This religious endorsement has contributed to its widespread adoption, particularly within Muslim communities, where it is perceived as both a spiritual and therapeutic intervention (El Sayed, Mahmoud, & Nabo, 2018; Rahmatullah, et al., 2021). Additionally, its affordability compared to conventional medical treatments makes it accessible across diverse socioeconomic groups (Xu, et al., 2020; Zhu, et al., 2021).

Aim of the Study

The increasing prevalence of wet cupping therapy (Hijama) in Karachi, Pakistan, highlights the need for a deeper understanding of the factors influencing its acceptance and public perceptions regarding its effectiveness. Despite its longstanding cultural and historical significance, limited scientific research has been conducted to evaluate these aspects (Al-Bedah, Elsubai, & Qureshi, 2019; Razzaq, Khan, & Zehra, 2013). This study aims to explore patient experiences, including reported therapeutic benefits as well as any adverse effects associated with the practice.

Objectives of the Study

To identify the social, cultural, religious, and therapeutic factors contributing to the growing adoption of Hijama therapy in Karachi, Pakistan.

To explore the responses and reported outcomes of individuals who have undergone Hijama therapy.

Material and Methods

Study Design

A prospective, cross-sectional survey.

Study Setting

The research was conducted in Karachi, Pakistan, involving various Hijama therapy centers across the city to ensure diverse representation.

Sample Size

It has been shown that the prevalence of cupping use among Saudi populations was very variable, ranging between 2.1% and 70.6% (Bhat, et al., 2024). Therefore, assuming a frequency of 35% with two-sided

confidence limits of 5%, a sample size of 350 patients was estimated, using an 80% power level and 95% two-sided significance level. A non-response adjustment of 10% has been added to adjust for lost or missing data.

Sampling Technique

A non-random convenient sampling technique was used to select the sample from the study population.

Data Collection Methods

A detailed questionnaire was designed to collect information on the demographics (age, gender, occupation, income level, living status), motivations for seeking Hijama therapy, specific health conditions treated with Hijama, and Feedback on the effectiveness and side effects of the therapy. All the patients who come for Hijama therapy in the Hijama clinics were first informed about the research and the after taking informed consent they were interviewed only once about the above factors.

Funding

Funding was not required in this study as only those patients were recruited who were already getting this therapy done by themselves.

Ethical Consideration

Information was given to all participants about the aims and objectives of this study. Any query raised by individual participants was clarified quickly. They will also inform them that this study is without any risk and their identity will remain anonymous. Answering the questionnaire will be considered as informed consent to participate in the study.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data like frequency and percentages were analyzed through excel sheets, while qualitative responses underwent thematic analysis.

Results

A total of 470 responses were collected from patients who had undergone Hijama therapy through randomized sampling. Among them, 82.1% were females, while 17.9% were males. The age distribution of participants revealed that 30.7% were between 40 and 49 years, 25.7% were aged 30–39, and 15.4% were aged 50–59 years. Only 8.3% of participants opted for Hijama therapy between the ages of 10–19 or 60–69 years, with a very low percentage beyond the age of 70.

Regarding living conditions, 51.2% of respondents lived in apartments. Most participants (56.1%) were housewives, while 14% were employed, 11.7% were students, and the rest had other occupations. The primary sources of information about Hijama therapy were family members or relatives (50%), followed by friends (40%), healthcare practitioners (9.4%), and media or the internet (7%). Table 1 shows the motivational factors for which hijama therapy was performed.

The Hijama procedure was performed by a trained doctor in 58.7% of cases, while 32.7% were treated by a trained therapist who was not a doctor. Additionally, 8.7% of procedures were performed by a family member knowledgeable in Hijama therapy, 6.7% by a herbalist, and 3.8% by any available individual. A small percentage indicated the therapy was conducted by religious scholars. Most participants (68%) underwent Hijama therapy at proper Hijama clinics, while 23.6% had it at their homes, 17% at the therapist's home, and 4.7% at mosques or religious schools (madrasas).

About 30% of respondents had been undergoing Hijama therapy for five years, 27% for more than ten years, and 25% for less than a year. Furthermore, 62.5% reported having multiple Hijama sessions in

their lifetime, while 15.5% did not recall, and 11% had undergone it only once. Figure 2 shows the frequency of hijama therapy done by the population.

Regarding knowledge about Hijama therapy, 69.2% believed that it could be performed on anyone, although 82.1% acknowledged that it may have side effects. Additionally, 68% of respondents expressed the opinion that Hijama therapy can cure all types of diseases. In 72.6% of clients, Hijama therapy was identified as the first choice for managing most of their health conditions, and this preference increased to 78.3% for specific diseases. Figure 2 identifies the percentage of various medical condition for which Hijama therapy was chosen.

The number of cups applied during each session varied. Approximately 28.3% of respondents had fewer than 10 or 20 cups per session, while 20% reported variable cup counts. Only 11% had more than 20 cups per session, and 12% had fewer than six cups per session.

Regarding the outcomes of Hijama therapy, 60.5% reported excellent results, 35% indicated good results, and very few noted no response. In terms of side effects 81.9% suffer different types of minor side effects, 38.8% experienced itching at the Hijama site, 22.4% reported blisters, 22.4% experienced pain, and 22.4% felt weakness. Other reported side effects included delayed healing (10.5%), fainting (6%), infection (6%), and bruising (4%).

Figure 1. Medical Therapies Integrated with Hijama Therapy by the Population

Table 1. Motivational Factors for Choosing Hijama Therapy

FACTORS	Number (Percentage)
1. Religious significance of Hijama therapy	326 (70.9%)
2. Perceived overall health benefits	264 (57.4%)
3. Hijama therapy has fewer side effects	123 (26.7%)
4. Hijama therapy provides quicker health benefits	84 (18.3%)
5. Hijama therapy is more affordable than conventional medicine	50 (10.9%)
6. Convenient and easily accessible	38 (8.3%)
7. Tried randomly to evaluate its effectiveness	22 (4.8%)
8. Frustration with conventional medicine	20 (4.3%)
9. Recommended or pressured by family members	17 (3.6%)
10. Popularity as a trending practice	14 (3%)

Figure 2. Frequency of Hijama Therapy by Population of Karachi, Pakistan

Figure 3. Medical Condition Treated with Hijama Therapy

Discussion

Hijama therapy, or wet cupping, has gained widespread recognition as a complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) practice. While its roots lie in cultural, religious, and traditional healing methods, its resurgence is largely driven by perceived health benefits, affordability, and minimal side effects (Al-Bedah et al., 2019). In Pakistan, particularly in Karachi, the increasing adoption of Hijama remains underexplored in terms of motivations, patient experiences, and global comparisons (Amber et al, Razzaq et al.) This study aimed to fill these gaps by evaluating the social, cultural, religious, and therapeutic factors influencing its practice.

A significant demographic trend observed in this study was the predominance of female participants (82.1%), aged between 30–49 years. This aligns with findings from Saudi Arabia and Malaysia, where women show a strong preference for traditional and faith-based healing methods (Alshahrani et al., 2020). The primary motivations for undergoing Hijama were religious beliefs (70.9%) and perceived health benefits (57.4%). Local studies, such as those conducted by Amber et al., confirm that both allopathic doctors and Hijama practitioners in Pakistan acknowledge the religious connection as a key driver of its popularity. This is consistent with global research emphasizing that religious beliefs play a crucial role in cupping therapy's acceptance (Ghazi, 2016; Alharbi et al., 2023). Additionally, Ibn Razali et al. (2021) highlight the presence of Muslim-friendly guidelines ensuring that cupping is performed in accordance with halal and ethical standards, enhancing its appeal.

Contrastingly, research from Western countries indicates that the primary motivation for seeking Hijama therapy is pain management and dissatisfaction with conventional pharmaceutical treatments (Xu et al., 2020). While only 4.3% of participants in Karachi cited frustration with modern medicine as a reason for choosing Hijama, this percentage is significantly higher in Western contexts, where concerns about drug dependency and side effects drive patients toward CAM therapies (Cao et al., 2019).

In terms of practitioner expertise, this study found that 58.7% of patients received treatment from trained practitioners, and 68% sought therapy in professional clinics. These findings align with research from the Middle East and Southeast Asia, where government regulations and licensing have enhanced the credibility of Hijama practitioners (El Sayed et al., 2018). However, Western countries continue to face challenges regarding the lack of standardized training and certification, limiting its integration into mainstream healthcare (Xu et al., 2020).

Regarding medical conditions treated, musculoskeletal pain (47%) emerged as the most common reason for seeking Hijama therapy. This corroborates global findings that wet cupping is widely used for conditions such as arthritis, lower back pain, and migraines (Rahmatullah et al., 2021). Local research also supports this, with Amber et al. highlighting that the most significant therapeutic outcomes in Pakistan were observed in musculoskeletal conditions. Other common conditions treated in this study included general relaxation (33%) and genitourinary issues (29%). Notably, studies from China and Iran emphasize Hijama's use in treating metabolic disorders such as diabetes and hypertension, indicating regional variations in its perceived therapeutic scope (Zhu et al., 2021).

Alharbi et al. (2023) and Ghazi (2016) report that patients experience substantial relief from headaches, migraines, back pain, and arthritis due to improved blood circulation facilitated by cupping therapy. The suction effect is believed to stimulate nerves and muscles, promoting relaxation and physiological rejuvenation (Ibn Razali et al., 2021). Many patients describe feeling energized post-treatment, attributing it to enhanced oxygenation and detoxification. This aligns with studies suggesting that cupping removes stagnant blood and impurities, thereby improving circulation and immune function (Al Marshedi et al., 2019; Niazi et al.).

This study found that 95.5% of participants reported positive outcomes, with 60.5% experiencing excellent results and 35% reporting good results. These satisfaction levels are consistent with findings from Turkey and Egypt, where over 90% of patients expressed contentment with Hijama's effectiveness in managing chronic ailments (El Sayed et al., 2018). However, minor side effects such as itching (38.8%) and localized pain (22.4%) were reported. Similar adverse reactions have been documented in global studies, underscoring the need for standardized hygiene protocols and post-procedure care (Alshahrani et al., 2020). Alharbi et al. (2023) and Ibn Razali et al. (2021) caution that improper cupping techniques can result in skin infections, bruising, and dizziness if performed by untrained practitioners, emphasizing the importance of regulatory oversight (Al Marshedi et al., 2019).

Treatment preferences varied, with 34.9% of participants combining Hijama with allopathic medicine, whereas 51.9% preferred it as a standalone therapy. This reflects differing healthcare perspectives; in Pakistan and other Islamic nations, Hijama is often viewed as a primary treatment due to religious and

cultural beliefs. Conversely, in Europe and North America, it is predominantly used as a complementary therapy alongside conventional medicine (Cao et al., 2019).

The number of cups applied during Hijama sessions varies based on patient condition, practitioner expertise, and therapeutic goals. Traditionally, between 5 to 10 cups are used for general health maintenance and pain relief in Middle Eastern countries, whereas Chinese and Iranian cupping therapies may involve up to 20 cups, particularly for musculoskeletal disorders (Zhu et al., 2021). Studies from Turkey and Egypt suggest that chronic conditions often require a higher number of cups over multiple sessions (El Sayed et al., 2018). Some practitioners adhere to the Sunnah-based method, applying 3 to 5 cups on specific points for overall well-being, while others target localized areas for specific conditions such as arthritis and sciatica (Rahmatullah et al., 2021). This study found significant variability in cup application, suggesting a lack of standardized protocols. Excessive use without proper assessment may lead to adverse effects such as bruising, prolonged pain, and increased sensitivity (Alshahrani et al., 2020).

In this study, patients often underwent Hijama therapy based on need but also adhered to Sunnah days, traditionally recommended on the 17th, 19th, and 21st of the Islamic lunar month, particularly when these dates fall on Monday, Tuesday, or Thursday. This practice is deeply rooted in Islamic tradition, as Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) endorsed these specific days for Hijama (Schmidt Stiedenroth, 2019). A study by Syahruramdhani et al. (2021) examined the physiological effects of performing Hijama on Sunnah versus non-Sunnah dates, finding a more favorable impact on vital signs when conducted on Sunnah days. While this suggests potential physiological benefits, there remains limited empirical evidence to conclusively prove their superiority. As a result, the **timing and frequency of therapy should be personalized** based on individual health needs and determined in consultation with qualified practitioners. Furthermore, the application of the Sunnah-day theory is generally considered relevant to healthy individuals, where toxin accumulation is believed to occur cyclically, rather than for those managing chronic diseases.

In practice, Hijama treatment plans are often **individualized**. Some practitioners recommend sessions once every three months for healthy individuals, particularly before seasonal changes or during hot weather. However, for those with specific health concerns, **more frequent sessions** may be necessary initially, with adjustments based on progress (HijamaRelief.com).

Conclusion

Despite growing acceptance of Hijama therapy, there is a need for standardized protocols regarding the number of cups used per session, timing and frequency of cupping along with broader regulatory measures to ensure the safety and effectiveness of Hijama therapy. Public awareness campaigns on side effects, hygiene protocols, and the importance of trained practitioners can further enhance treatment outcomes and patient safety. Additionally, comparative clinical trials assessing Hijama's efficacy against conventional medicine could provide stronger evidence for its integration into mainstream healthcare (Zhu et al., 2021).

Limitations

This study faced challenges such as self-reported biases and limited generalization due to the sample being confined to Karachi. However, these will be mitigated by ensuring diverse representation and robust analysis.

Future Recommendations

Future research could focus on randomized controlled trials to establish the clinical efficacy of Hijama therapy across various conditions, enabling better regulation and integration into healthcare systems.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest between authors.

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